

THE CONCEPT OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND ITS ROLE IN SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY.

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Annotation. Conducting scientific research is a rationally organized creative activity with its own methods and techniques. Its rationality is connected with the perception of the human mind and the requirements of real life, and its methodology and methods are based on the methods and mechanisms accepted in science that help to effectively carry out creative activity. Scientific research is the ability of a person to constantly be ready to understand changes in himself and his environment, to come out of his shell on the basis of a new way of thinking. The result of scientific research is scientific knowledge. The desire to invent new things shows the theoretical presence of the scientist.

Key words: Scientific research, search for oneself, scientific adviser, Startup, Introduction.

Scientific research is a unique form of scientific research that depends on the creative courage and perseverance of the researcher. The researcher must be armed with the advanced ideas of his time, be an independent thinker, have a high level of knowledge, be a lover of innovation. Scientific research is a complex, fascinating and controversial process. The researcher conducts research under internal (sensory-cognitive, spiritual, intellectual) and external (objective world, social relations, society) influences, it is not easy to direct these influences to a scientific goal. A person who has mastered the methodology of scientific research, who is well versed in scientific methods and knows how to use them, achieves the intended goal and can express an important opinion in the field of science.

The main purpose of scientific research is to bring the real state of the object (subject) to an ideal state. The task of the scientist is to find effective ways and mechanisms to achieve this goal and offer it to society.

The steps leading to the choice of the subject of scientific research can be called the period of "self-search" of the researcher, "search for oneself." During this period, the researcher is still far from choosing a topic and linking it to the problem. Experience shows that it is rare to find a researcher who finds a topic and relates it to a problem when he first enters the field of science. Therefore, in choosing a topic, the help and advice of a specialist who is well versed in the field of science, research and problems related to the topic is needed. Such a specialist is called a "scientific adviser", "scientific consultant", "mentor", who teaches the rational conduct of research, since he is aware of the objective factors that influence the choice of topic.

The objective factors that determined the choice of the topic are:

- the need for social development;
- the demand for scientific and technological progress;

- the need for a social and political system;
- factor of economic development;
- the need for cultural improvement.

It is an axiom that science serves social progress. Therefore, the chosen topic should be related to the goals and objectives of social development.

Social progress means the overall development of man, the preservation and enhancement of universal human values, the greater humanization of social life, the solution of global problems, the further enhancement of human achievements and positive experience. Only by serving these goals and objectives, science, ongoing research, the chosen topic acquire a positive value.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the concept of the development of science until 2030 was approved. Development of social partnership between the state and scientific organizations through the development of a system of self-government in science and the implementation of projects within its framework. in terms of improving the system of financing science and scientific activities and diversifying sources of funding:

By 2025, increase the share of total funds allocated to science in relation to the gross domestic product by 6 times, and by 2030 - by 10 times;

By 2025, increase the share of private sector funding for research and development from the current 8 percent to 20 percent, and to 30 percent by 2030; in 2021 year 2, in 2025 10 venture organization of funds;

In accordance with the above-mentioned resolution, in cooperation with leading foreign investment companies, in order to finance Startup projects, financial support and benefits were implemented for the implementation of Startup projects: Kalbiev Najibulla, a teacher at Korakolpok State University, a new start-up project was implemented and in this project a new economical building of heaters, boilers. (katyol) was presented and in this start-up project was estimated at 600 million soums, as a result, 30 jobs were created.

Conclusion.

The role of scientific research in scientific activity poses new tasks and questions for science, for example, the development of science for a specific social goal. At present, scientific research and research are the main form of development of modern science. If we understand that science is a force that contributes to the development of society, that is, a tool that serves the development of society, the people, the state, an important factor and starting point for all technical and economic transformations in society, then scientific research and research are of great importance and will lead the state to new height.

The research methods presented in this manual can be divided into two groups:

the first - general scientific research methods used in all sciences (research);

the second - private scientific research methods used in individual disciplines.

Justification of the relevance of the topic, the definition of a research concept is a prerequisite for scientific research in all areas. Experiments, systematic functional analysis, surveys and modeling are not used in all areas of science. Therefore, each senior researcher, independent researcher chooses methods of scientific research based on the topic, concept, object (subject) of research. The chosen method should serve the purpose of the study.

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